

Better4U

Preventing obesity through Biologically and bEhaviorally
Tailored inTERventions for you - BETTER4U

D1.1 Project kick off-meeting

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Executive Summary

BETTER4U aims to unveil the interplay between obesity biological and lifestyle determinants. The project aims at closing the current gap between research and effective personalized interventions for obesity prevention, via use of modern monitoring tools and artificial intelligence and machine learning practices. The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a detailed description of the proceedings of the project's kick-off meetings, held in Athens, Greece, on November 2nd and 3rd 2023, with the combined in-person and online participation of the 28 international and multidisciplinary consortium partners from Europe, Israel and Australia (20 in-person and 8 online team attendances). During this two-day meeting, HUA presented the scientific basis and organizational structure of the project, each leader presented the proceedings that are outlined in their corresponding work package and action points on next steps were jointly discussed and agreed.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

1. Purpose and Agenda of the Meeting

The BETTER4U kick-off meeting was carried out on November 2-3, 2023, marking the onset of the project's lifecycle. The 28 consortium partners from Europe, Israel and Australia, joined the proceedings either in in-person or online format, for this two-day hybrid meeting. The purpose of the gathering was: i) to coordinate and discuss the necessary actions on setting the foundations for the project's beginning; ii) to thoroughly present the tasks and activities of each work package (WP) and further underline their interconnections; and iii) to agree on specified next steps for the project scientific and organizational governance.

The meeting's final agenda is presented below (section *1.1.Meeting Agenda*). During the first day of the meeting, the HUA team thoroughly presented the scientific scope of the project, the overall proceedings of all WPs during the 4-year duration of the project, as well as the cornerstones of its structural governance. Day two included dedicated sessions for each WP, where WP leaders presented all corresponding tasks involved, followed by extended discussions and brainstorming on the optimization of the relevant WP's practical proceedings (section *1.2.Meeting Minutes*).

Both days' sessions were recorded, as a means to facilitate rapid exchanges and sufficient updating of all partners who could not attend in-person or who were unavailable due to the time difference.

Finally, a press release highlighting the main content of the project was shared in Harokopio University of Athens' [official Instagram page](#), while public posts were also shared by multiple consortium partners using the twitter hashtag #BETTER4U_EU, which was created by the European Food Information Council (EUFIC) as WP9 leader (*WP9: BETTER4U Methodology Guidelines for Personalized Lifestyle Recommendations, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan*).

1.1. Meeting Agenda

 ΧΑΡΟΚΟΠΕΙΟ ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ
HAROKOPIO UNIVERSITY

 **Prevention of obesity
throughout the life course**

HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-01-05-two-
stage

Project No: 101080117

Preventing obesity through
Biologically and bEhaviorally
Tailored inTERventions for you |
BETTER4U

Kick-Off Meeting (KoM) Agenda

2-3 November 2023 |
Harokopio University of Athens,
Athens, Greece

Preventing obesity through Biologically and bEhaviorally Tailored inTERventions for you | **BETTER4U - KoM**

THURSDAY, NOVEMBER 2ND

KARABATZOS AUDITORIUM

11:00 – 15:00

- Optional Attendance at Harokopio University of Athens Pre- and Post- Graduate Graduation Ceremonies

14:00 - 15:00

- Welcome Coffee

15:00

- Official **BETTER4U Kick-off Meeting Start**

15:00 – 15:15

- **Opening Remarks**
 - Prof Mara Nikolaidou, Rector, Professor of Information Systems and Systems Engineering, Harokopio University of Athens
 - Prof Yannis Manios, Dean of School of Health Science and Education, Professor in Nutritional Education – Nutritional Assessment, Harokopio University of Athens

15:15 – 16:15

- **Keynote Speech - Introduction to BETTER4U Consortium and the HUA Team**
 - Prof Georgios Dedoussis, Vice Rector of Academic Affairs and Quality Assurance, Professor of Molecular Genetics – Nutrigenetics, Harokopio University of Athens, BETTER4U Coordinator

16: 15 – 17:15

- **Icebreaker Activities & Introduction to BETTER4U Scientific Goals and Management**
 - Dr Maria Kafyra, Postdoctoral Researcher, Harokopio University of Athens

ATHENS CITY CENTRE

20:00

- BETTER4U Kick-Off Meeting Dinner

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FRIDAY, NOVEMBER 3RD

KARABATZOS AUDITORIUM

10:00 – 10:20

- **Opening Remarks**

- Prof Georgios Dedoussis, Vice Rector of Academic Affairs and Quality Assurance, Professor of Molecular Genetics – Nutrigenetics, Harokopio University of Athens, BETTER4U Coordinator

10:20 – 12:00

- **Introduction to BETTER4U Work Packages (WP) 2 to 6**

10:20 – 10:40

- **WP2 Ethics, Legal and Regulatory Compliance**

- Mag. Lisa Marie Breyer and Rodessa May Marquez, MA, University of Vienna, WP2 Leader

10:40 – 11:00

- **WP3 Identification of Biological Determinants of Weight Gain: The BETTER4U dataset**

- Prof Anders Eriksson, Associate Professor of Interdisciplinary Research in Genomics, University of Tartu, WP3 Leader

11:00 – 11:20

- **WP4 Lifestyle and socio-cultural determinants of weight gain: a synthesis of evidence**

- Professor Aleksandra Luszczynska, Professor of Psychology, SWPS University of Social Sciences and Humanities, WP4 Leader & Dr Ioanna Panagiota Kalafati, Postdoctoral Researcher, Harokopio University of Athens / University of Thessaly

11:20 – 11:40

- **WP5 Development of the BETTER4U causal AI Model for Weight Gain**

- Prof Stavroula Mougialakou, Head of Artificial Intelligence in Health and Nutrition Lab., University of Bern, WP5 Leader & Prof Christos Diou, Professor of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, Harokopio University of Athens

11:40 – 12:00

- **WP6 Continuous & Objective Monitoring and a Pilot Study**

- Prof Anastasios Delopoulos, Professor of Multimedia Systems, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, WP6 Leader

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FRIDAY, NOVEMBER 3RD

KARABATZOS AUDITORIUM

12:00 – 13:00

- Coffee Break

13:00 – 14:20

- **Introduction to BETTER4U Work Packages (WP) 7 to 9**

13:00 – 13:20

- **WP7 Implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the BETTER4U Lifestyle Personalized Intervention**
 - Prof Yannis Manios, Dean of School of Health Science and Education, Professor in Nutritional Education – Nutritional Assessment, Harokopio University of Athens

13:20 – 13:40

- **WP8 Evaluation of the long-term cost-effectiveness and budget impact of the novel BETTER4U intervention**
 - Prof Nick Verhaeghe, Professor of Health Economics, Dr Ruben Willems, Post-doctoral researcher, University of Gent, WP8 Leader

13:40 – 14:20

- **WP9 BETTER4U Methodology Guidelines for Personalized Lifestyle Recommendations, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Plan**
 - Darya Silchenko and Stephan Kampshoff, European Food Information Council , WP9 Leader

14:20 – 15:00

- **Discussion and Closing Remarks**
 - Prof Georgios Dedoussis, Vice Rector of Academic Affairs and Quality Assurance, Professor of Molecular Genetics – Nutrigenetics, Harokopio University of Athens, BETTER4U Coordinator

KALLITHEA, ATHENS

15:00 – 17:00

- BETTER4U Kick- Off Meeting Lunch

1.2. Meeting Minutes

Location: “Karabatzos” Auditorium, Harokopio University, Athens, Greece

Thursday, November 2, 2023:

3:00 pm Opening Remarks and introductions

Opening remarks about Harokopio University of Athens (HUA), and the significance of the BETTER4U project by:

- Professor Mara Nikolaidou, Rector of HUA, Professor of Information Systems and Systems Engineering
- Professor Yannis Manios, Dean of the School of Health Science and Education, Professor in Nutritional Education and Nutritional Assessment, HUA
- Professor Georgios Dedoussis, Vice Rector of Academic Affairs and Quality Assurance, Professor of Molecular Genetics and Nutrigenetics, HUA, BETTER4U Coordinator

The opening remarks were followed by brief introductions by all the other participants of the meeting.

4:00 pm Keynote Speech - Introduction to BETTER4U Consortium and the HUA team by Professor Georgios Dedoussis

Professor Georgios Dedoussis’ presented his CV and research activities and proceeded to present the prevalence and heritability of obesity. He noted that so far very few studies have taken into account both lifestyle and genetic factors, and that is a research gap.

4:30 pm Overview of the BIO-STREAMS project presented by E. Vellidou.

BIO-STREAMS (project title: Multi-Pillar Framework for children Anti-Obesity Behavior building on an EU biobank, Micro Moments and Mobile Recommendation Systems) is another HORIZON project aiming to deliver an integrated ecosystem comprised of:

- a) The first EU Childhood/Adolescence Obesity Biobank, acting as an EU-wide data-sharing centre for research and innovation, hosting real & synthetic data.
- b) An Accessible Obesity Platform combining the Biobank with a public user interface, and an extensive AI-based toolkit.
- c) An EU Community Network on Childhood/Adolescence Obesity.

Eleftheria Vellidou presented the expected outcomes of BIO-STREAMS, its partners and its synergies with the BETTER4U project, such as investing in an ecosystem featuring community characteristics.

5:00 pm Proposal of BETTER4U logos by EUFIC

Stephan Kampshoff and Darya Silchenko briefly presented two different options for the BETTER4U logo, and asked all participants to prepare to vote on one of them on November 3rd.

5:10 pm Overview of the OBCT project

Professor J. Lakerveld of Amsterdam UMC presented the objectives and expected outcomes of the OBCT project, a consortium of 12 partners from Europe aiming to

provide health professionals, policymakers, researchers, and the public with new knowledge, maps and tools that support sustainable prevention of obesity and the reduction of inequalities therein by socioeconomic position. OBCT is another project that has synergies with BETTER4U, such as common partners and objectives.

5:30 pm Introduction to BETTER4U Scientific Goals and Management by

Dr Maria Kafyra, Postdoctoral Researcher at HUA presented the following characteristics of the project:

- Descriptions and timeline of phases 1-4
- Reporting and Payment Periods
- Governance Structure
- Responsibility Assignment Matrix
- Administrative Timeline (General Assembly and Dissemination Committee Meetings)
- Management Gantt Chart
- Work Breakdown Structure
- Work Package 1 Tasks
- First Year Deliverables
- Progress of GA, CA, prefinancing, and JCAs

Friday, November 3, 2023:

10:00 am until 3:30 pm Introduction to BETTER4U Work Packages 2 to 9 by the WP leaders

WP2 Ethics, Legal and Regulatory Compliance

Lisa Marie Breyer & Rodessa May Marquez presented the University of Vienna (UNIVIE) team and WP2 tasks, partners involved, objectives, and the deliverables and milestones timeline.

They declared the UNIVIE team will make sure the project and in particular the handling of personal data complies with the legislation of the EU as well as any state's legislation that applies to the BETTER4U consortium. Soon they will have lead meetings about the consent forms, which data will be open, etc.

WP3 Identification of Biological Determinants of Weight Gain: The BETTER4U dataset

Prof. Anders Eriksson, Associate Professor of Interdisciplinary Research in Genomics, University of Tartu, presented the WP3 objectives, task structure, leaders and contributors.

The main aim of WP3 is to leverage diverse information from longitudinal and cross-sectional studies to map biological determinants of weight gain and weight loss.

The objectives of WP3 are the following:

1. Collate publicly available resources (such as summary statistics and epigenetic data) relevant for the project.
2. Implement a system of federated analysis across data-providing partners that will also serve as a platform for analyses in WP4 and WP5.

3. Perform multi-trait meta-analysis of genetic determinants of weight gain and identify key structural variants in RNA and proteins, as well as regulatory mechanisms (such as gene expression and splicing variation), involved in these processes.
4. Provide input based on these findings for the development of novel predictive tools for weight gain and weight loss in WP5.

WP4 Lifestyle and socio-cultural determinants of weight gain: a synthesis of evidence

Professor Aleksandra Luszczynska, Professor of Psychology, SWPS University of Social Sciences and Humanities, WP4 Leader & Dr Ioanna Panagiota Kalafati, Postdoctoral Researcher, HUA/University of Thessaly, task 4.4 leader, presented the WP4 objectives, task structure, and task leaders.

The objectives of WP4 are the following:

1. To synthesize evidence on efficacy and acceptability of genetic risk communication strategies used in the context of weight change and obesity (T4.1)
2. To synthesize evidence on associations between lifestyle factors and weight gain in vulnerable populations (low socioeconomic position, disability, ethnic minority, etc.) (T4.2)
3. To aid understanding of associations between lifestyle factors and weight gain in the context of characteristics of local environment, socioeconomic position, and mental health, by individual level and meta-analysis from the BETTER4U datasets (T4.3 and 4.4).

WP5 Development of the BETTER4U causal AI Model for Weight Gain

Professor Stavroula Mougiakakou, Head of Artificial Intelligence in Health and Nutrition Lab., University of Bern, WP5 Leader & Christos Diou, Professor of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, HUA presented the WP5 objectives, tasks, deliverables, milestones, partners, SWOT Analysis, and its interrelation with other WPs.

WP5 aims to develop an AI-based causal model for weight gain using:

1. the findings of WPs 3 & 4,
2. the BETTER4U 1M retrospective dataset and
3. data collected from a prospective BETTER4U pilot (T6.3).

The model will define and quantify causal relationships between variables that are associated with weight gain and obesity, including genetics, biological/anthropometric, behavioural/lifestyle, and environmental variables. The causal model will allow predictions on the outcomes of interventions, as well as counterfactual estimation, thus facilitating the development of individualized, optimal interventions by health care professionals.

WP6 Continuous & Objective Monitoring and a Pilot Study

Professor Anastasios Delopoulos, Professor of Multimedia Systems, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki presented the WP6 goals, leaders, contributors, task structure, deliverables, bottlenecks/risks, as well as its interrelation with other WPs.

WP6 aims to:

- Design and Implement Behavioral and Environmental indicators
- Complement the Biological profile of subjects
- Develop the Better4U monitoring platform
- Develop the Better4U clinical dashboard
- Run a pilot study with continuous monitoring

The presentation of WP6 was followed by a discussion of the participants about the implementation of the BETTER4ALL pilot study, and in particular how the tools will be used for the monitoring of the study subjects, and the purpose of the use of the tools during the pilot study. This discussion will be continued in future meetings.

WP7 Implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the BETTER4U Lifestyle Personalized Intervention

Professor Yannis Manios, Dean of School of Health Science and Education, Professor in Nutritional Education and Nutritional Assessment, HUA, and Dr. Eva Karaglani, Senior Research Associate at Harokopio University of Athens, presented the WP7 participants, objectives, task structure, deliverables, and milestones.

The main objective of WP7 is to implement and assess the effectiveness of the BETTER4ALL personalized intervention in:

- Assisting individuals to adhere to the hypocaloric dietary plan and PA recommendations;
- Achieving the desired weight loss within the 6-month proposed period; and
- Further maintain this weight loss for a period of 12 months following intervention conclusion.

The presentation of WP7 was followed by a discussion of the participants about the timeline of the BETTER4ALL intervention.

WP8 Evaluation of the long-term cost-effectiveness and budget impact of the novel BETTER4U intervention

Dr Ruben Willems, Post-doctoral researcher at the University of Gent, presented the WP8 task structure, leaders, contributors, and deliverables. He explained which costs would recur in a RL-implementation, how the cost-effectiveness analysis will be implemented, how the obesity-related cost savings will be estimated.

WP9 BETTER4U Methodology Guidelines for Personalized Lifestyle Recommendations, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Plan

Dr Darya Silchenko and Dr Stephan Kampshoff, of the European Food Information Council (EUFIC), presented the EUFIC team, mission, and activities. They proceeded to explain the WP9 task structure, contributors and objectives, and asked the KoM participants to vote on the two options for the BETTER4U they had presented the previous day. The participants voted via slido.com.

Closing the KoM, Dr Silchenko and Dr Kampshoff encouraged all participants to write down ideas on the BETTER4U project's benefits they would like to be communicated to obesity patients, their families, health professionals, policy makers, insurance companies, scientific community, and others.

2. Photos

Several pictures of the two-day BETTER4U Consortium meeting can be seen below.

Picture 1. Group photo of the consortium members in HUA.

Picture 2. Group photo of the consortium members in HUA.

Picture 3. Presentations and discussion among the consortium partners.

3. Conclusion and Next Steps

The BETTER4U kick-off meeting was completed successfully, noting the official, landmark beginning of the project. Emphasis was given in the organization of all proceedings surrounding the use of data, as outlined in work packages 3,4,5, and 6, as well as the systems and methodology required for the necessary analyses. Over the coming months, ethics and legal matters surrounding data use will be prioritized and further emphasis will be placed on the onset of the first analyses, along with the simultaneously ongoing dissemination activities. The next consortium meeting will take place at the end of June 2023.